

Clear view on a turbid estuary (HBOTE)

Technical report

Annex to HBOTE final report Phase 1

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2017-10-02

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AC	Atmospheric correction
ACOLITE	Atmospheric correction of Operational Land Imager (and MSI)
BBM	Benthic biomass
C2RCC	Case-2 Regional / Coast Colour Processor
CDOM	Coloured dissolved organic matter
CHL	Chlorophyll-a (chlorofyl-a)
COAH	Copernicus Open Access Hub
CODA	Copernicus Online Data Access
GHRSSST	Group for High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature
LST	Land surface temperature
MODIS	Moderate-resolution imaging spectroradiometer
MSI	Multispectral Instrument onboard of Sentinel 2
OC5	Five channel chlorophyll concentration algorithm
OLCI	Ocean and Land Colour Instrument onboard of Sentinel 3
OLI	Operational Land Imager onboard of Landsat 8
PAR	Photosynthetically active radiation
S2	Sentinel 2
S3	Sentinel 3
SLSTR	Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer onboard of Sentinel 3
SPM	(Total) Suspended particulate matter
SST	Sea surface temperature

1. Scope

The project HBOTE ('Heldere blik op troebel estuarium', which translates as 'Clear view on a turbid estuary') explores the feasibility to set up an Earth Observation (EO) based service to monitor parameters which are required as input for primary production estimation in the Dollard estuary.

For the aims, social context, technical and financial feasibility, a summary of the results and the conclusions of the project we refer to the final report of phase 1: 'HBOTE Eindrapport fase 1'. This technical report describes the materials, methods and detailed validation results of this phase.

1.1. Confidentiality

This technical report is added as an annex to the final report phase 1. The original of this report was confidential.

Adjustments between the original version and this public version:

- This section 1.1
- Page 20 re-formulation [marked in blue]

2. Earth Observation data and processing methods

2.1. Data and methods

As proposed in the project plan, HBOTE studied three Earth Observation (EO) datasets:

- A low-resolution dataset with a high frequency, derived from specific 'ocean colour' sensors. This dataset will serve to analyse the variation in time and space of the required parameters on a large scale. It is expected that the water quality parameters in this dataset will be most precise.
- A medium-resolution dataset with a medium frequency derived from multispectral sensors. With this dataset we evaluate the (changes in) spatial variability of the processes in the water and on the tidal flats.
- A high-resolution data set with a low frequency, derived from high resolution sensor(s). This dataset will evaluate the high spatial variability of the benthic microalgae.

The satellite data is processed according to a general scheme (Figure 1), however, with different algorithms per sensor and parameter.

Figure 1, general processing chain for EO data.

In Tables Table 1 (low resolution), Table 2 (medium resolution) and Table 3 (high resolution) an overview is provided of which satellite sensor data is included, and which algorithms were tested for processing of this data.

During validation (chapter 3), the best combination of algorithms was chosen (in bold in tables Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3. These algorithms were applied to derive the final products.

*Table 1 Low resolution dataset. Best algorithm combination per parameter in **bold**.*

Parameter	Sensor(s) / source	Spatial resolution	Atmospheric correction	Algorithms tested	notes
SST	Multiple sensors/ GHRSSST	1km		GHRSSST	Interpolated in case of clouds
PAR	OLCI / CODA	300m	OLCI standard	OLCI standard PAR product	
SPM	OLCI / CODA	300m	C2RCC	Nechad 2010	
CDOM			C2RCC	C2RCC	
Kd			C2RCC	C2RCC, Cobios (Blaas et al, 2013)	
CHL			C2RCC	Gons 2005 , OC5	
LST	SLSTR / CODA	1km	SLSTR standard	SLSTR standard LST product	
Sediment type	OLCI / CODA	300m	OLCI standard	WI, this report	
BBM			OLCI standard	Kromkamp 2006	

*Table 2: Medium resolution dataset. Best algorithm combination per parameter in **bold**.*

Parameter	Sensor(s) / source	Spatial resolution	Atmospheric correction	Algorithms tested	notes
SST	OLI / USGS	100m	Barsi 2005	Barsi 2005	
SPM	MSI / COAH	10m	C2RCC, C2X , Acolite	C2RCC / Nechad 2010	
CDOM			C2RCC, C2X , Acolite	C2RCC	Experimental product
Kd			C2RCC, C2X , Acolite	C2RCC	
CHL			C2RCC, C2X , Acolite	C2RCC, Gons 2005	
LST	OLI / USGS	100m	Barsi 2005	Barsi 2005	

Sediment type	MSI / COAH	10m	Sen2Cor	WI, this report	
BBM			Sen2Cor	Kromkamp 2006	

Table 3: High resolution dataset

Parameter	Sensor(s) / source	Spatial resolution	Atmospheric correction	Algorithms tested	notes
SPM	RapidEye/ Satellite data portal	5m	MODTRAN	Based on Nechad 2010	Qualitative estimate
Sediment type				WI, this report	
BBM				Kromkamp 2006	

The processing is largely automated, based on tools such as SNAP, in combination with WI’s own Python and C scripts in a flexible and scalable processing environment. For the new sensors (S3 OCLI and the high resolution optical sensors) processing scripts were set up within HBOTE. Details of C2R, C2RCC and C2X algorithm can be found in Brockmann et al, 2016.

2.2. Data availability

One year of data is produced as example dataset. A year provides the best insight in seasonal effects, which determine primary production to a large extent. The chosen period is September 2016-August 2017. This choice is based on a) the availability of Sentinel-3 OLCI data, which has spectral bands that are very suitable for retrieval of coastal water quality parameters, and b) the high resolution optical data (Planet, Triplesat, RapidEye), which is made available by the satellite data portal, which is required for the analysis of spatial distribution of benthic microalgae. Not all datasets are available for a full year yet due to the delayed release of the different processing levels of Sentinel-3 OLCI data. It is expected that the earlier data will become available within the next few months.

Figure 2 provides an overview of the data which was available and processed for each sensor over the chosen year.

Figure 2, overview of the availability of the different satellite data.

3. Validation data and methods

3.1. Validation setup

A proper method for accuracy control for EO-based products is essential for the development of operational water quality services. We have therefore collected a large in situ data set (section 3.2) to perform these analyses. From these in-situ data, pairs of ‘matchups’ were selected. Matchup is defined here as a pair of an in situ measurement (concentration of a water constituent or a spectral measurement) measured in the same time span and location as a satellite image. The time span considered here is ± 15 min for in situ spectral measurements and ± 60 min for in situ concentrations. In case in-situ data were collected continuously (interval of ~ 2 minutes) we averaged the points within the overpass time span to represent the in-situ data point matching the satellite pixels. The match up data set is the verification ‘ground truth’ against which the EO products are validated.

Because the largest amount of light that is captured by satellite sensors is reflected by the atmosphere, it is essential to remove the atmospheric effects from the signal (atmospheric correction). The accuracy of water quality products is largely (>95%) dependent on the atmospheric correction methods and algorithms (Salama and Stein 2009, Salama et al., 2011, Salama 2012). Only in a second step, the concentrations of the parameters can be derived from the atmospherically corrected signal.

Therefore, the validation was split in two levels:

- 1) inspection of the atmospheric correction and
- 2) inspection of the uncertainty in water quality products

For level 1, verification of the atmospheric correction, matchups between satellite pixels and in-situ reflectance data are needed. Close-range sensors use the same sensing technology as earth-observing satellites with their platforms being just few meters above the water target. This is opposite to orbital and geostationary satellites that normally operate at altitudes of ~ 800 km and ~ 3600 km, respectively. This low altitude implies that the data acquired by close-range sensors are free of atmospheric influences and can, therefore, be used as benchmark for atmospheric correction and retrieval models. Because there is no spectral data of the study area itself within the period of interest, spectral data the automated TRiOS sensors at the NIOZ (also Wadden Sea) are used.

For level 2, verification of the accuracy of water quality products from EO data, two paths are followed:

- I. Comparison of parameters derived from EO data with in-situ data from the match up dataset. This comparison covers level 1 and level 2 validation simultaneously. However, because of cloud cover in the satellite data and the low temporal resolution of the in situ data (most parameters are obtained every 2 weeks), this match up set is rather small to base any statistically sound conclusions on.
- II. To increase the size of the dataset for validation of the parameter-retrieval algorithms, the accuracy of these algorithms is also tested on a set of ‘matchups’ of in-situ reflectance data and concentrations. The HBOTE consortium has access to a large set of these in-situ reflectance vs. concentration matches (section 3.2).

3.2. In situ data

The following in-situ datasets were collected, and where needed quality controlled.

Close-range spectral data (in situ reflectance data)

Automated TriOS measurements of water, at the NIOZ jetty station on Texel (NJS) for the years 2015 and 2016. This data is used for atmospheric correction validation of S2 MSI (level 1). The processing methods for these data can be found in the [COLOURS documentation pages](#) (accessed 18 September 2017).

TriOS measurements of water, from the PhD thesis of A Hommersom (2010). This dataset also contains the concentrations measurements (TSM, CDOM, Chl). This dataset is used for verification of parameter retrieval algorithms from spectral data (level 2). Detailed processing methods of this data can be found in Hommersom et al, 2009.

TriOS measurements of tidal flats and water, taken by the INPLACE project. This data also contains the concentration of Chl-a, sediment type and benthic biomass. Detailed processing methods of this data can be found in Matchup_data_Processing_Report_nr2_V01.pdf, which is delivered at the same time as this report.

The close-range spectra were convolved to Sentinel 3-OLCI (S3) and Sentinel 2-MSI (S2) spectral bands, before the parameter-retrieval algorithms were applied.

In-situ parameter data

Laboratory data

For chlorophyll-a and TSM, measurements were retrieved from the MWTL data set via the Waterbase public web service for the following stations in or close to the study area:

- Bocht van Watum
- Groote Gat Noord
- Huibergat oost
- Rottumerplaat 3 km uit de kust

These data are lab analyses based on water samples taken during measurement cruises about once a month. Data are currently only available until 2016.

Data from the permanent measurement stations

Data from the permanent measurement station at Knock, in the German part of the Eems estuary, were provided by NLWKN via RWS. The data are TSM values derived from an automated online sensor of turbidity that delivers data every five minutes. Data are available from 01/2015 – 07/2017.

Data from the automated measurement station at Eemshaven owned by RWS were provided for a list of satellite matchup times. For each matchup, data at a 1-minute time interval were provided for a time window of 3 hours around the actual satellite overpass time. Data include, amongst other parameters, Chl-a and turbidity measurements. For water temperature, data from a number of online sensors in the study area, but also in the wider Wadden Sea, were retrieved via the Waterinfo web service. These data are measured at a 10-minute interval

3.3. Validation methods

As described in section 3.1, two levels of validation are applied: inspection of the atmospheric correction (1) and inspection of the uncertainty in water quality products (2). With the in-situ data which was collected in HBOTE, for most parameters both levels of validation could be performed (Table 4). As can be seen, only for a few parameters (PAR, CDOM, Kd and LST), there was no suitable in-situ data available of the area. For these

parameters, only the atmospheric correction could be validated, and suitable algorithms were applied based on expert knowledge and literature.

Table 4, Overview of which parameters are obtained at which resolution, from which sensors, which validation data was available and which validation level (section 3.1) was performed.

Parameter	Low resolution	Medium resolution	High resolution	Validation data set	Validation (level)
SST	GHRSSST	OLI	-	RWS	In situ vs satellite (1+2)
PAR	OLCI	-	-	-	-
Reflectance	OLCI	MSI	RapidEye	TriOS at NIOZ (matchups only for MSI)	In situ spectra vs satellite spectra (1)
SPM	OLCI	MSI	RapidEye	RWS in situ, Permanent stations, PhD thesis A Hommersom	in situ spectral vs in situ concentrations (2), In situ concentrations vs satellite (1+2)
CDOM	OLCI	MSI	-	-	-
Kd	OLCI	MSI	-	-	-
CHL	OLCI	MSI	-	RWS in situ, Permanent stations, INPLACE project, PhD thesis A Hommersom	In situ spectral vs in situ concentrations (2), In situ concentrations vs satellite (1+2)
LST	SLSTR	OLI	-	-	-
Sediment type	OLCI	MSI	RapidEye	Sediment atlas Deltares	Sanity check, comparison of spatial patterns
Benthic biomass	OLCI	MSI	RapidEye		

Validation of atmospheric correction

For the S2 MSI instrument, three AC methods (Acolite, C2X and C2RCC) were applied to S2MSI images over water target. The validation was based on matching the atmospherically corrected S2MSI observations to in-situ measurements collected from the NIOZ jetty station (NJS) for the years 2015 and 2016.

Statistical measures, e.g. root mean square of relative error and determination coefficient, slope and intercept of Type-2 regression, are used to assess the validity of the AC results. The equation used for the root mean square of relative errors is $RMSRE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum (1 - \frac{x}{y})^2}$

For S3 OLCI, no matchups with in situ reflectance measurements were available for validation of the atmospheric correction. However, the same atmospheric correction was used as was found to be the best performing method for S2.

Validation of parameter retrieval

We describe the goodness of fit (GoF) between measured and retrieved values using type II regression (Law 1997), the coefficient of determination, R^2 , the mean absolute differences (MAD) and the relative MAD (rMAD)

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in [%]. High accuracy in the retrieved values yields type-II slope $\rightarrow 1$, type-II intercept $\rightarrow 0$, $R^2 \rightarrow 1$ and $MAD \& rMAD \rightarrow 0$. The symbol " \rightarrow " means that approaches.

Scatterplots were made, from which statistical measures, such as root mean square of relative error and determination coefficient, slope and intercept were retrieved. Also, time series were created. Time series proved a better insight in the variability and frequency of both data sources.

4. Validation results

4.1. Validation of atmospheric correction of Sentinel-2-MSI over water

Matchups

In total there were 13 matchups between S2MSI observations and NJS in-situ measurements: 7 for Acolite, 9 for C2X and 10 for C2RCC.

Acolite processor results

The atmospherically corrected spectra, using Acolite, are averaged, per band, and plotted against the averaged in-situ spectra in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Acolite: Validation result of mean spectra

Figure 4. Acolite: Validation result of actual spectra.

Acolite spectra are underestimated (overcorrected), in particular for 490-705 nm bands. Bands of longer wavelength and the blue band at 443 have less overcorrection. The underestimation of Acolite is about 54% (the slope). The RMSRE is 29% for all bands. This RMSRE is for the mean values, the RMSRE for actual values is higher ~52%. Figure 4 shows the validation per band (coloured symbol).

C2X processor results

The validation results of C2X for the mean and actual values are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6 respectively. Figure 5 shows that C2X results are much better than Acolite, for the mean values however. C2X slightly overcorrect (about 10%) the S2MSI spectra, with RMSRE of 26%.

Figure 6 shows the validation with respect to actual spectra. The RMSRE is now 55% (compare to the 26% in Figure 4) with data points closer to the 1:1 line.

Figure 5. C2X: Validation result of mean spectra.

Figure 6. C2X: Validation result of actual spectra.

C2RCC processor results

The validation of C2RCC are shown for the mean and actual spectra in Figure 7 and Figure 8. The resulting spectra are underestimated (by about 32%) and RMSRE of 31%. Figure 7 shows that C2RCC is deriving very low values of Rrs, i.e. over correcting with large RMSRE ~66%.

Figure 7. C2RCC: Validation result of mean spectra.

Figure 8. C2RCC: Validation result of actual spectra.

Summary and conclusions atmospheric correction of S2 MSI over water

The mean values of the resulting spectra are plotted in Figure 9. It is clear from Figure 9 than only C2X falls within the variability range of the in-situ measurements. In addition, the C2X mean spectrum has an apparent absorption feature at B4 = 665 nm.

Figure 9. Mean values of the resulting spectra. The dashed lines (u/l) are the upper and lower bounds of in-situ spectra. Aco stands for Acolite.

Table 4 summarizes the statistical measure of the mean spectra. Table 5 shows the same measures used in table 1 but for the actual values.

Table 4: Validation measures for the mean spectra.

	Acolite	C2X	C2RCC
Slope	0.54	0.9	0.69
Intercept [sr ⁻¹]	6E-06	-0.0023	-0.0019
R ²	0.99	0.98	0.98
rMAD [%]	29	26	31

Table 5: Validation measures of actual spectra.

	Acolite	C2X	C2RCC
Slope	0.46	0.90	0.74
Intercept [sr ⁻¹]	0.0008	-0.0023	-0.0023
R ²	0.67	0.76	0.78
RMSRE [%]	52	55	66

Table 4, Table 5 and Figure 9, show that the best results were obtained from C2X.

4.2. Parameter retrieval validation

Based on close-range remote sensing

The Nechad-705 model (Nechad et al., 2010) was employed to retrieve SPM concentrations, whereas for Chla the Gons model (Gons 2005) was employed. We used the models as they are without tuning. *Figure 10* and *Figure 11* show the comparisons between S3 and S2 retrievals of SPM and Chla.

Figure 10, SPM retrieved from close-range remote sensing versus in situ SPM concentrations

Figure 11, Chl retrieved from close-range remote sensing versus in situ Chl concentrations

The validation of retrieved values is shown in Table 6 in the form of goodness of fit (GoF) values. From Table 6, Figure 10 and Figure 11, we conclude that SPM and Chla retrievals are comparable for both sensors (S2 and S3) with a slope of ~ 0.2 , meaning that retrievals are one-fifth of the measured values, and rMAD $\sim 55\%$. Retrieved Chla values have, however, slightly higher accuracy than SPM, with higher slope ~ 0.5 , $R^2 \sim 0.7$ and rMAD $\sim 35\%$. This relatively large difference between measured and close-range retrievals is attributed to two main reasons:

- The models were calibrated with measurements from waters with different biochemical compositions than that of the Wadden Sea.
- Close range measurements are automatic and contain errors that are not accounted for:
 - i. Specular reflection of wave facets that was not accounted for in the correction procedure.
 - ii. Focusing and defocusing of the light beam at the sensor due to waves, which were not properly averaged.
 - iii. Variable illumination conditions.

These errors are mainly attributed to the small footprint of close-range sensing, thereby affecting the retrieval of the (back)scattering coefficient, a primary input/coefficient to the Nechad-705 and to a lesser extent to Gons models. That the Gons model is less affected by these errors is the main reason behind obtaining higher accuracy in Chla retrievals.

Due to pixel averaging, these errors are expected to be of less influence on satellite retrievals with, however, residuals introduced by spatial mismatch and atmospheric correction.

Table 6. Validation of retrievals from close range remote sensing.

GoF	SPM [g.m ⁻³]		Chla [mg.m ⁻³]	
	S3	S2	S3	S2
Slope	0.22	0.21	0.56	0.52
Intercept	11.38	12.08	2.11	5.39
R2	0.44	0.41	0.70	0.71
MAD	21.00	21.04	5.72	4.45
rMAD [%]	56.00	56.25	37.84	31.71

Based on satellite matchups

This data set consists of satellite observations, from Sentinel 3-OLCI sensor (S3-OLCI) and Sentinel 2-MSI sensor (S2-MSI), and matching in-situ measurements of SPM and Chla concentrations. The satellite data were atmospherically corrected using C2RCC (S3) and C2X (S2) model, as it was concluded from the validation of atmospheric correction (section 4.1). In addition to Nechad-705 model we applied the concentration retrieval within the C2RCC and C2X models and inter-compared the results. The C2RCC is a “closed” plugin that is intended to process satellite images and, therefore, could not be used for close-range remote sensing data.

Figure 12, Comparisons between SPM retrievals of S3-OLCI using Nechad705 and C2RCC models

Figure 13, Comparisons between SPM retrievals of S2-MSI using Nechad705 and C2X models

From Figure 12, Figure 13 and the associated GoF values in Table 7, we conclude that S3-OLCI SPM retrievals from the Nechad-705 model are accurate with a slope that is ~ 9% off unity and acceptable R² ~0.67. Although C2RCC/C2X SPM retrievals show higher R² value, they are about 3 folds larger in magnitude than measured values with high error rMAD ~150%. The validation of S2-MSI SPM retrievals (Figure 13), are less accurate for both models, with Nechad-705 yielding better results.

Table 7, Validation of SPM retrievals from satellite data.

Gof	SPM [$\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$]			
	S3-OLCI		S2-MSI (< 100)	
Model	Nechad-705	C2RCC	Nechad-705	C2RCCX
Slope	0.91	3.51	0.35	2.40
Intercept	-4.74	-20.32	3.05	-31.15
R ²	0.67	0.82	0.71	0.87
MAD	8.73	43.75	26.48	38.80
rMAD	38.23	159.77	54.55	80.04

Chl-a validation could, unfortunately, not be performed due to unrealistic in-situ measurements, as shown in Figure 14. - retrievals from S3-OLCI using Gons model shows realistic seasonal variations, whereas in-situ data are noisy with either high ~ 156 or low < 5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ values. Details of this issue are discussed in section 4.5 ‘errors in in situ data’.

Figure 14, Comparisons between satellite retrieval of Chla and in-situ data from the continuous measurement station.

Conclusions and recommendation parameter retrieval validation

The validation results presented in this chapter show that [in this situation] SPM retrievals from close-range remote sensing [were] slightly less accurate than those derived from satellite images. This improved accuracy, on the one hand, confirms the discussed sources of error in close-range data and, on the other hand, shows that atmospheric correction errors are mainly attributed to over/under corrections of haze.

Error due to over/under corrections of haze propagates to satellite retrievals, with main contribution to SPM through the (back)scattering coefficient. In addition to atmospheric correction, the comparison of in-situ point measurement (water volume of ~5 liters) with satellite pixel (water volume between 10 m³ for S2-MSI and 9000 m³ for S3-OLCI) is largely biased. One way to compensate this spatial mismatch is through using continuous in-situ data (e.g. each 2 min for two hours covering the satellite overpass) and employing longer time series of matchup.

Our results present the first attempt to validate “off-shelf” retrievals models with automated in-site data, with the main conclusion that Nechad-705 and Gons model provide more accuracy than C2RCC/C2X. As such there is a wide range of improvements that should be applied in order to increase the usability and capability of satellite derived product for the Eems Dollard Estuary. These future improvements will include, but not limited to:

- 1- Recalibrate the models to represent the bio- physical/chemical characteristics of the Wadden Sea, particularly the Eems Dollard estuarine waters.
- 2- Investigate the automated in-situ data to provide a more realistic validation results and account for errors due to data noise, spatial mismatch and atmospheric correction.
- 3- Use longer time series of matchups to correct the bias in of retrievals. This is particularly useful for the operationalization of earth observation products, as sensors on earth orbiting platforms degrade with time.

4.3. Grain size

As a basis for developing an algorithm for detecting grain size indicators in the Wadden Sea and Dollard estuary we started with the best documented dataset available, which is the “Sediment Atlas Wadden Sea”. This dataset is made available by Gerben de Boer as [netCDF file in the OpenEarth Server at Deltares](#).

A MATLAB script was created to read the data in the netCDF file. The basic available data is:

- ID Number
- Latitude
- Longitude
- Per ID number there are 26 particle diameter classes (expressed as phi = -log₂ (grainsize in mm)) (Table 8).

Table 8, Particle diameter as phi value.

particle_diameter as phi_value			
"1 of 26" -20.0	"10 of 26" 25.0	"19 of 26" 70.0	
"2 of 26" -15.0	"11 of 26" 30.0	"20 of 26" 75.0	
"3 of 26" -10.0	"12 of 26" 35.0	"21 of 26" 80.0	
"4 of 26" -5.0	"13 of 26" 40.0	"22 of 26" 85.0	
"5 of 26" 0.0	"14 of 26" 45.0	"23 of 26" 90.0	

"6 of 26"	5.0	"15 of 26"	50.0	"24 of 26"	95.0
"7 of 26"	10.0	"16 of 26"	55.0	"25 of 26"	100.0
"8 of 26"	15.0	"17 of 26"	60.0	"26 of 26"	105.0
"9 of 26"	20.0	"18 of 26"	65.0		

Per particle size class the percentage is given of the sample grains that fall into this size class. The file also provides the cumulative phi value for the all the size classes. From the data we calculated the following percentages:

- 1) D10 is the point (phi value) where the cumulative Phi plot reaches the value 10
- 2) D50 is the median grainsize (as phi) determined from the point where the cumulative Phi plot reaches the value 50
- 3) D90 is the point (phi value) where the cumulative phi plot reaches the value 90.
- 4) %Clay: $\text{phi} \geq 8$
- 5) %Silt: $4.0 \leq \text{phi} \leq 7.9$
- 6) %Sand: $-1.0 \leq \text{phi} \leq 3.9$
- 7) %Coarse: $-20 \leq \text{phi} \leq -1.1$

In the first phase of HBOTE we only used the D50 value for further calculations. The approach to building a D50 algorithm for Sentinel 2 was as follows:

From literature it was assessed that topographic altitude will be an important factor in sediment grain size. The sorting effects of wind and currents will probably leave higher grain sizes at relatively higher places in the estuary, while mud will collect probably at the intertidal mudflats (as we also see in practice). It is also assessed from literature that bigger grains (sand) have higher reflectance than smaller grains (mud) because of the difference in material, shape of the grains and organic content. Grain size detection is hampered when vegetation is covering the surface. The problem with using the sediment atlas data to devise an algorithm is the fact that the data is quite old. Our first attempt to design a simple and robust algorithm was to correlate satellite observed S2 NDVI values (as a more or less constant indicator between images) and actual bathymetry to the older sediment atlas observations, assuming (hoping) that the original distribution of sand/mudflats etc has not changed completely in the area. A very good cloudless image at high solar zenith angle (2nd June 2017) was selected to obtain NDVI values at Sediment Atlas locations. The Bathymetry map downloaded from EMODNET was also sampled at these locations.

The following equation was obtained:

$$D50 = 27.31 - 1.55 * NDVI - 1.62 * Z$$

For the following boundary conditions:

- 1) $Z \leq 0$
- 2) $NDVI > 0$ and $NDVI \leq 0.4$
- 3) $D50 \leq 40$

Figure 15, D50 derived from one S2 image (2017) versus D50 from the sediment atlas.

As can be expected from correlating the old sediment atlas data to one recent S2 image data, the correlation coefficient is very low (Figure 15). Still the equation is workable since it produces a robust first estimator of D50, which can be improved if more calibration/validation would come available. For interpretation purposes: If D50 is high: the sediment is mud and around D50=20: the sediment contains a small portion of sand.

The size distribution derived from the EO data compares well with a map as found in literature (Figure 46).

4.4. Validation of temperature

SST

Sea surface temperature was obtained from low resolution and medium resolution sensors (Figure 16, Figure 17).

Figure 16. SST from low resolution data versus in situ

Figure 17. SST from medium resolution data versus in situ

For both data sources, the correlation between EO-based and in-situ SST is quite good. From the statistics (Table 9), it becomes clear that the SST is best retrieved with the low resolution data. However, the low resolution dataset is also much larger (because of a higher observation frequency), which also influences the statistics.

Table 9. Statistics for SST retrieval for low and medium resolution data

Resolution	R ²	slope	intercept	R	P	standard error	RMSE
Low	0.93	0.93	0.68	0.96	8.155e-182	0.014	1.39
Medium	0.67	0.81	1.56	0.82	0.001	0.180	0.63

Some examples of time series for low resolution SST are shown in Figure 18 and Figure 19. For most of the time, the EO-derived SST and the in situ SST follow each other closely. Only late May and early June 2017, there is a discrepancy between the trends at Eemshaven. This period is also cause of the data points in the scatterplot (Figure 16) to be slightly off the 1:1 line. The weather data (collected by KNMI at Nieuw Beerta) showed a slight dip in temperature late May like the EO data, but did not have really the same pattern as either of the two water temperature plots, so the air temperature could not clarify which one of the two SST datasets was correct. However, the in situ SST data has a gap directly after the period with the discrepancy (June/July), so it could be that the instrument needed cleaning or re-calibration.

Figure 18. Time series of SST from buoy and GRSSST at Eemshaven

Figure 19 Time series of SST from buoy and GRSSST at Randzelgat Noord

For the high resolution SST retrievals, examples of time series are shown in Figure 20 and Figure 21. Clearly, the in situ data at Uithuizerwad are quite variable, as the water temperature varies with tide in the shallow areas. The few matching Landsat-8 results show within the measured range.

Figure 20 Time series of SST from buoy and Landsat-8 at Uithuizerwad

At Amelander zeegat, the SST from satellite data falls nicely on the time series plot of the in situ data.

Figure 21 Time series of SST from buoy and Landsat-8 at Amelander zeegat buoy

The land surface temperature from low resolution data was studied, but tidal flats were not considered as land within the S3 LST processing chain. This made these products not suitable for the purpose of HBOTE. There is no LST in situ data available for validation of the medium resolution LST.

Errors in situ data

In this report we focus on the results of the EO-derived data, and the potential issues on its quality. The in situ data is used as reference, and generally assumed to be correct. However, also the in situ data can contain errors. An example of this is shown in Figure 22 and Figure 23, which show data from the automated measurement station at Eemshaven at two days that seems erroneous. Figure 24 shows the longer term developments in concentrations, demonstrating that the 160 µg/l observed at the continuous station in November, or the 80 µg/l observed at the continuous station in April are indeed much higher than the expected amounts. The data of these days are therefore not suitable for validation purposes. However, other in situ data sources might also contain erroneous data which was not discovered.

Figure 22. Chlorophyll data from the automated measurement station at Eemshaven, 2016-11-28.

Figure 23. Chlorophyll data from the automated measurement station at Eemshaven, 2016-04-03.

Figure 24. Chl data at three mwtl stations over a longer period, from Lin, Y (2016).

4.5. Discussion on validation

Although the validation of the satellite results is generally very promising (previous sections), there are also some discrepancies. From the validation, also the differences in properties of the data series becomes clear. We will list the most important differences, with their respective (dis)advantages and reasons for differences, plus the possibilities of errors in the in situ data.

Differences in methods

Between in situ data sources, various methods are used, all with their own uncertainties. For example, for chlorophyll, mwtl samples are analysed in a laboratory (www.aquo.nl), probably with HPLC, while chlorophyll from a buoy is derived with a fluorometer. Before validation of the MERIS satellite results, these methods were compared by Sørensen et al (2007). They demonstrate that the variance between laboratories for coastal waters varied from 10 to 16% for HPLC and from 5 to 20% for the spectrophotometric results.

There are also intrinsic differences between these determination methods. For HPLC, samples are taken in situ, transported to the lab and filtered. Next, the pigments are extracted from the cells on the filter, and these are determined via liquid chromatography. In the process of transport, filtration and extraction, few pigments will get lost. The chromatographic method is based on molecule size, so that only chlorophyll-a molecules are measured. Because of the manual processing of the samples, the derived concentrations are vulnerable to random errors.

The fluorescence method that is applied on a continuous station, is fully in situ. A light signal is sent through the continuously refreshed water sample, and a receiver on the other side of the tube catches the fluorescence signal of the pigments. No transport, filtration or extraction is needed. However, calibration of a fluorescence sensor is complex, especially because they need to be calibrated for a 'matrix' of components, while the concentrations of e.g. SPM are quite variable in the Ems estuary. Also biofouling can have a disturbing effect on these measurements. These issues would lead to an (increasing) systematic error. In contrast to HPLC, also some of the breakdown products of chlorophyll-a produce similar fluorescent light and will therefore also be measured.

This means that data from lab and continuous stations will not be related as 1:1. The satellite data has its own determination method, and uncertainties. The satellite measures light which originates from the sun, is passed through the atmosphere, through the water surface and gets (partly) absorbed by pigments. The remaining light is scattered on water molecules or suspended particles, and passed back through the surface and the atmosphere, to the satellite. Because chlorophyll-a absorbs at specific wavelengths, the concentration can be determined based on the size of the absorption dip. In contrast to the two in situ methods, the satellite receives information from the upper layer of the water, instead of from a specific depth. The light that is received depends on the transparency: the deeper the Secchi depth, the deeper the water column from which light will be received. From a validation perspective, this makes it difficult to compare the satellite results with measurements from other methods. From a user perspective, the EO results are received from the photic depth, and therefore useful for deriving primary production. The uncertainty of the EO-based results mainly lies in the atmospheric correction, because the atmosphere has the largest influence on the light that is scattered back towards the sensor. The atmospheric correction validation results were discussed in detail in section 4.1.

Spatial differences

The spatial extent of a sample from EO data and in situ data is an important reason for differences between the two. In situ concentration results, either from sampling campaigns or from a continuous station, are point measurements, while the satellite data delivers pixels. The advantage of the satellite imagery is that an overview of the complete area can be obtained. However, because of the pixel-based results, there will always be an intrinsic difference between the two sources. Depending on the spatial resolution of the satellite instrument, the information of a 'sample' is averaged over a few meters (RapidEye) to 1 km (GRSST). Depending on the purpose and the parameter, this might be an advantage or a disadvantage. Averages over a pixel size of some tens of meters reduces the chance of including local disturbances into the results (e.g.: suspended matter measurements from a ship can easily be disturbed by the mixing effects of the engine of the ship itself), which is an advantage of satellite data. However, around the tidal flats, pixels containing a mixture of a surfacing tidal flat and water are a concern: proper flagging of suspect pixels is therefore important to avoid error in the derived concentrations.

Clearly, the resolution needs to be chosen carefully for each parameter. Additionally, the satellites with the highest resolution generally only produce data with a lower frequency, which needs to be taken into account when choosing the most suitable resolution. In the final report we will make some preliminary recommendations for the best satellite data source for different parameter.

Differences in acquisition frequency

The frequency is also an important property of each of the data sources. However, when data from the same moment in time are compared (see section 4.1 ‘matchups’) the frequency of data availability does not have an effect on the validation results. It does influence the number of data points that are available for validation though. For example, in Figure 21, SST from medium resolution data versus in situ SST, only one data point of the high resolution data matches with the in situ data. Therefore, the scatterplot with validation results (*Figure 17*) contains relatively little data. This is, on the other hand, a very good example of two complementary datasets. The in situ SST data is very frequent in time, but is recorded at only at a few points (buoys and poles). Although there is only one matching data point from the in this time series plot, the spatial distribution of the medium resolution temperature data adds new dimension to the SST data (*Figure 71, Figure 72, Figure 75*).

5. Results

5.1. Benthic mapping

Benthic biomass

Low resolution imagery is acquired frequently: for example, Figure 25 and Figure 26 were taken within two days. The S3 image at February 13th was acquired at 10:39 CET, while it was low tide at 8:08 CET. The image at February 15th was acquired at 11:28 CET, while it was low tide at 9:06 CET. Both therefore represent a status of incoming tide.

Figure 25. Low res. BBM, 17 February 2017

Figure 26. Low res. BBM, 15 February 2017

Although less frequent, more spatial details can be found in the medium resolution imagery. Two almost cloud free S2 images were acquired at low tide (Figure 27, Figure 28). At 26 August 2016 the S2 image was acquired at 12:40 CEST, while low tide at Delfzijl occurred at 12:26 CEST. At 2 June 2017, the S2 acquisition time was 12:40 CEST, while low tide at Delfzijl occurred at 12:27 CEST.

Figure 27. Medium res. BBM, 26 August 2016

Figure 28 Medium res. BBM, 2 June 2017

The difference in resolution is even more pronounced when zooming in to an area like the Dollard (Figure 29, Figure 30). These maps show that the benthic biomass seems to grow best in the areas on the deeper parts of the tidal flat, along the (tidal) shorelines.

Figure 29, Low res. BBM, detailed view

Figure 30, Medium res. BBM, detailed view

Also from the very high resolution data, benthic biomass can be derived (Figure 31, Figure 32, Figure 33). Only a few patches are visible, because of the tidal phase. In the Dollard (Figure 32), the areas are cut-off with the cut-off of the image. These products, derived from RapidEye, show a similar pattern and the same range of concentrations as the low resolution and medium resolution results. The detailed view (Figure 32) shows that the high resolution does not show any more detailed patterns than the medium resolution imagery (Figure 30).

Figure 31, High res. BBM, 27 May 2017

Figure 32, High res. BBM, detailed view

Figure 33, High res. BBM, 27 March 2017

Tidal flats (NDVI)

The differences in the total area of surfacing tidal flats is illustrated by Figure 34 and Figure 35. As mentioned earlier, the S3 image of February 15th was acquired during incoming tide. At July 17th, the S3 image was taken at high tide (11:49 CEST, high tide at Delfzijl at 12:07 CEST).

Figure 34, Low res. tidal flats, 15 February 2017

Figure 35. Low res. tidal flats, 17 July 2017

As with the benthic biomass, the low resolution data lacks the details that are visible in the medium resolution tidal flat maps (Figure 36, Figure 37).

Figure 36. Medium res. tidal flats, 26 August 2016

Figure 37. Medium res. tidal flats, 2 June 2017

Figure 36 and Figure 37 show that it is not only the tidal phase which affects the surface of the tidal flats that is exposed. Although the tidal phase was the same for the two images, the image acquired at June 2 shows a much larger surface of the tidal flats than the image of August 26. These differences are caused by differences in amplitude in the tidal cycle, but also by effects of the weather (mainly wind direction).

Figure 38, High res. tidal flats, 27 March 2017

Figure 39, High res. tidal flats, 27 May 2017

Also from high resolution data, grain size can be derived (Figure 39, Figure 38). Like for BBM, the area is cut-off in the Dollard because the image is cut-off, and the patterns are similar to those derived from the medium resolution data (e.g. Figure 37).

Grain size

Grain size is expressed in phi. The scale of phi is inverse to the grain size. A phi of 8 or higher can be compared with a grain size smaller than 62.5 μm , which is clay.

As expected, the grain size seems to be rather constant over time (Figure 40, Figure 41).

Figure 40, Low res. grain size, 15 February 2017

Figure 41, Low res. grain size, 17 July 2017

The patterns and absolute values of the grain size compare very well between low resolution (Figure 40, Figure 41), medium resolution data (Figure 42, Figure 43) and – for the portions that are visible - high resolution (Figure 44, Figure 45).

Figure 42. Medium res. grain size, 26 August 2016

Figure 43. Medium res. grain size, 2 June 2017

Figure 44, High res. grain size, 27 May 2017

Figure 45, High res. grain size, 27 May 2017

The patterns of grain size also well match the patterns as known from literature (Figure 46).

Figure 46 Median grain size of sediment taken from Gotje et al., 2017

5.2. Water quality parameters

SPM

Figure 47, Low res. SPM, 10 March 2017

Figure 48, Low res SPM, 11 March 2017

At March 10, a S3 image was acquired one hour after high tide at Delfzijl (acquisition 11:32 CET, high tide at 10:19 CET), followed by one at 11 March at the almost exact moment of high tide (acquired at 11:06, high tide at 11:19 CET). The difference between these products clearly shows that the currents of the ebb tide cause a lot of resuspension just after high tide. This was also shown in Hommersom et al. (2009), where concentration changed from around 10 mg m^{-3} to around 60 mg m^{-3} at a station near Rottummerplaat. According to KNMI data, both days had comparable wind speeds, which confirms that the difference must be due to tide.

Figure 49, Medium res. SPM, 16 January 2017

Figure 50, Medium SPM, 27 March 2017.

On January 16th, there is little light available due to the low solar angle. This leads to a relatively noisy S2 image (Figure 49), although the values and distribution are reasonable. The image was acquired at 11:54 CET, while it was high tide at Delfshaven at 14:15 CET; it was therefore incoming tide. At 27 March 27th, the S2 image (Figure 50) was acquisition at 12:50 CEST, while it was high tide at 12:12 CEST. In the Dollard area, at the tidal flats close to Delfzijl and the area south of Rottummerplaat, sediment is being resuspended because the tide starts to go out. In the deeper area, the water is still relatively clear after North Sea water was brought in during high tide.

High resolution data (RapidEye) could also be used to map SPM (Figure 51, Figure 52). The patterns are as expected, however, the absolute values could not be validated, so results are presented in a qualitative way.

Figure 51, High res. SPM, 27 March 2017

Figure 52, High res. SPM, 27 May 2017

Chl

For Chl, there is also an effect of outgoing tide (Figure 53, Figure 54), although the effect is smaller than for SPM.

Figure 53, Low resolution Chl, 10 March 2017

Figure 54, Low resolution Chl, 11 March 2017

For S2, the image of January 16th is slightly noisy because of the low solar angle, but also because the chlorophyll algorithm uses a ratio of bands at two different resolutions, which causes a noisy effect (Figure 55). By smoothing (Figure 56) this effect can be removed. In the data package, the originals without smoothing are included.

Figure 55, Medium res. Chl, 16 January 2017

Figure 56, same as Figure 55, but smoothed

Also for the product of January 16th, smoothing was applied to the S2 Chl product of March 27th.

Figure 57, Medium res. Chl, 27 March 2017

Figure 58, same as Figure 57, but smoothed

The chlorophyll maps can be used to trace sources of chlorophyll. Figure 59 shows the discharge plume of the Westerwoldse Aa (in the south of the Dollard), and Figure 60 shows higher concentrations in the Zeehavenkanaal which comes from the harbour of Delfzijl and Oude Eemskanaal (in the middle of the image, southern side).

Figure 59, Medium res. Chl, detailed view

Figure 60, Medium res. Chl, detailed view

CDOM

The CDOM product, as shown in Figure 61 and Figure 62, is an un-validated test product. The concentrations are within the range found in literature, and also it is known that outgoing tide, such as captured in the image of 11th March, brings CDOM from the inland areas towards the sea. However, the values are expected to be higher in the Dollard area and lower towards the North Sea. Therefore, the pattern is not completely as expected.

Figure 61, Medium res. CDOM, 11 March 2017

Figure 62, Medium res. CDOM, 11 March 2017

Figure 63, Medium res. CDOM, 16 January 2017

Figure 64, Medium res. CDOM, 27 March 2017

K_d

The level and spatial distribution of K_d is as expected, both for the low resolution products (Figure 65, Figure 66) and for the medium resolution products (Figure 67, Figure 68). Higher values occur in the Dollard area and along the tidal flats, lower values in the German bight, north of the islands.

Kd, 10 March 2017
Sentinel-3

Figure 65, Low res. Kd, 10 March 2017

Kd, 11 March 2017
Sentinel-3

Figure 66, Low res. Kd, 11 March 2017

Kd, 16 January 2017
Sentinel-2 - smoothed

Figure 67, Medium res. Kd, 16 January 2017

Kd, 27 March 2017
Sentinel-2 - smoothed

Figure 68, Medium res. Kd, 27 March 2017

5.3. Temperature and PAR

For the water temperature (SST) and the temperature on the tidal flats (LST) the seasonal changes are much larger than the spatial differences. To still be able to see spatial differences, the scalebars are adjusted and different per image.

Sea surface temperature

For water temperature, imagery with high and low resolution were available for the same days, allowing a good comparison. The water temperature maps with the low resolution (Figure 69, Figure 70) and the medium resolution (Figure 71, Figure 72) show the same pattern and scale.

Figure 69, Low res. SST, 13 February 2017

Figure 70, Low res. SST, 15 September 2017

The medium resolution reveals much more detail: in winter, the shallow areas are colder (Figure 71), while in late summer (Figure 72), the shallower areas are warmer. This makes sense, as the temperature differences on land and tidal flats are larger than in the water.

Figure 71, Medium res. SST, 13 February 2017

Figure 72, Medium res. SST, 15 September 2016

The differences between image capture at one moment in time (medium resolution) and as aggregate (GHSST) becomes clear from comparing (GHSST) and (L8), captured at the same day, while L8 was captured at relatively low tide, causing the tidal flats to show up, and clearly warmer water at the shallow locations, while for GHSST the image is available for the whole area, but showing an average at unknown time.

Figure 73, Low res. SST, 6 September 2016

Figure 74, Medium res. SST, 6 September 2016

Land surface temperature (tidal flats)

Like for water temperature, the seasonal differences in LST are larger than the spatial differences. The colour scale is therefore adjusted per image. There is a good match between the land and the water temperature products of the same day: Figure 75 (LST of February 13th) matches well with Figure 71 (SST of February 13th), and Figure 76 (LST of September 6th) matches well with Figure 74 (SST of February 6th).

Figure 75, Medium res. LST, 13 February 2017

Figure 76, Medium res. LST, 6 September 2017

PAR

PAR does not show much spatial variation (Figure 77, Figure 78), however, around the clouds the values are somewhat lower. The clouds itself are shown as no data in the maps.

Figure 77, Low res. PAR, 17 July 2017

Figure 78, Low res. PAR, 15 September 2017

5.4. Conclusions and recommendations

For conclusions and recommendations we refer to the final report of HBOTE fase 1 (HBOTE Eindrapport fase 1).

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